

foundingGIDE Technical Event 2024 Report

Project Title	Founding a Global Image Data Ecosystem
Project Acronym	FoundingGIDE
Project Number	101130216
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Project Duration	30 Months

Summary

The first foundingGIDE technical event was held in person at RIKEN, Kobe, Japan in 2024. The event gathered developers, ontologists, researchers, and image data experts worldwide. It combined a hackathon with two parallel workshops on data management and image analysis.

Key insights

The first foundingGIDE technical event “foundingGIDE BioImage Hackathon” was an in-person developer event hosted at the RIKEN institute in Kobe, Japan from 4th to 8th of November 2024. The event brought together developers, ontologists, researchers, and image data experts from around the globe.

Figure 1. Summary of the event ([technical event webpage](#), [detailed agenda](#))

The technical coordination event combined a hackathon in parallel with two workshops focused on data management and image analysis. The hackathon served as an essential continuation of the discussions and connections made during the [foundingGIDE Community Event 2024](#). The practical, hands-on nature of the hackathon enabled participants to collaboratively develop

solutions for these challenges while the workshops allowed participants to learn new skills around data management and image analysis.

Figure 2. Technical event opening by Shuichi Onami and participants attending the session

Hackathon

The foundingGIDE technical event convened in Kobe, Japan, brought together international experts to address key challenges in bioimaging data interoperability and standardization. Multiple focused working groups were established, each tackling a specific theme relevant to ontology integration, metadata representation, and FAIR data packaging. This report summarizes the main outcomes of the five working groups.

Working group	Contributors, Goals, Achievements, Next steps
Ontology deep dive: FBbi & EDAM	<p>Project contributors: Hiroshi Masuya, Koji Kyoda, Adriaan Ludl, Caterina Strambio De Castilla, Aastha Mathur, Francois Sherwood</p> <p>Goals: Compare two imaging method ontologies: FBbi and EDAM BioImaging, for use in metadata standards to represent the 'type of imaging that was used to capture a specific image'</p> <p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FBbi has better structure for this specific problem, despite less coverage of imaging methods. ● Generation and manual review of a mapping for all relevant terms in FBbi to terms already covered in EDAM BioImaging. ● Created a tool to map classes from one taxonomy to another based off the manual mapping: <p>Next Steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reach out to FBbi owners (as it is currently inactive) to see if we can get proposals into FBbi and ownership transfer due to ongoing development being required as new imaging methods develop.

<p>OMERO-RDF</p>	<p>Project contributors: Josh Moore, Maria Mirza</p> <p>Goals: Expand the plugin for exporting RDF data from OMERO (omero-rdf) to allow the generation of JSON-LD and more specifically RO-Crate Object</p> <p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working version (PR#25) of JSON-LD and RO-Crate output (Subsequently released as 0.5.0) • Tested the RDF generation against the IDR which is used during the schema.org review. • Trained new OMERO-RDF developers <p>Next Steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the following, de.NBI hackathon (Kassel, Dec 9-13), the work will continue to refactor the JSON-LD context used by omero-rdf. • Establish a working group to continue the development of the JSON-LD context and publish the context for others to consume.
<p>schema.org review</p>	<p>Project contributors: Josh Moore, Matthew Hartley</p> <p>Goals: Evaluate schema.org fields for their utility as GIDE, specifically BIA & IDR, terms in the JSON-LD context.</p> <p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due to time constraints, the focus was on all properties of type Person (and to a lesser extent, Organization). • All fields of those types were evaluated against BIAD-667 as an example. • Many fields can effectively be mapped to schema.org fields, increasing the richness of the fields. • Detailed results are on the “schema.org” tab of the FoundingGIDE Ontologies-REMBI spreadsheet <p>Next Steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate all other fields, possibly on a base-type basis. • Make use of identified fields in the JSON-LD context.
<p>Ontologies for Imaging+</p>	<p>Project contributors: Aybuke Kupcu Yoldas, Koji Kyoda, Eusike Dohi, Alexandra Zakieva, Ken Ho</p> <p>Goals: Compare different ontologies for chemical compounds (PubChem and CHEBI) and genes (NCBI gene and Ensembl) and see if they can be mapped to each other. These ontologies were chosen as they’re used by SSBD and IDR.</p>

	Achievements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no easy mapping as all four ontologies checked are very extensive and they all are very valuable. Decision was to support all and map to each other where possible. More here.
REMBI in RO-Crate	Project contributors: Aybuke Kupcu Yoldas, Koji Kyoda Goals: Add more REMBI terms in RO-Crate based on the mapping of SSBD and IDR fields to REMBI Achievements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A small example RO-Crate JSON producing code that includes a compound and gene example using schema.org and REMBI mapping https://github.com/foundingGIDE/zarr-crate

Workshops

As part of the foundingGIDE Technical Event, two in-depth, hands-on workshops were organized to provide participants with practical training on key tools supporting bioimaging data management and analysis. These workshops not only strengthened technical knowledge within the community but also fostered dialogue around best practices, tool integration, and workflow optimization. The two workshop that took place were: OMERO workshop and ilastik workshop.

Figure 3. Jean-Marie Burel (left, first image) and Petr Walczysko (right, first image) leading the OMERO workshop and Dominik Kutra leading the ilastik workshop.

OMERO Workshop

Led by the Open Microscopy Environment (OME) team, including Petr Walczysko and Jean-Marie Burel, participants engaged in hands-on sessions to install and configure their own OMERO servers. OMERO is a powerful open-source platform that enables robust image data

management. This track sparked productive discussions around deployment, troubleshooting, and optimization of OMERO for organizing large imaging datasets. Participants gained practical experience in deploying OMERO and ideas to integrate it into their workflows for managing biological imaging data.

Ilastik Workshop

Led by Dominik Kutra, this track provided hands-on training with ilastik, a machine-learning-based image analysis tool. Participants explored its applications in automated pixel- and object-level segmentation, classification, and tracking. Attendees learned how to apply ilastik to automate complex image segmentation tasks, a critical need for large-scale image analysis workflows.